

THE ROLE OF MASHRAB CREATIVITY IN UZBEK CLASSICAL LITERATURE AND ITS HISTORICAL AND ARTISTIC SIGNIFICANCE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the place and indelible work of Boborahim Mashrab in Uzbek literature. It analyzes the factors that formed Mashrab's personality and work in the Uzbek literary environment of the 17th-18th centuries, his mystical and philosophical views, his poetry in a folk spirit, and his literary style based on free thought. Divine love, human freedom, protest against social injustice, and the expression of the people's pain are shown as the leading themes in Mashrab's work. As a result of the research, it is scientifically revealed that Mashrab's work is an important stage in the development of Uzbek literary thought, and his works provided the ideological and artistic enrichment of our national literature..

One of the great figures of Uzbek classical literature, Boborahim Mullavali oglu Mashrab, left an indelible mark on the history of literature with his prolific work, courageous thought, patriotic spirit, and works rich in the philosophy of Sufism. His poetic heritage has not only literary and aesthetic value, but also spiritual and educational power. Mashrab is recognized as one of the most free, bold, and freedom-loving poets in Uzbek literature. The poet's life and work are closely connected with Sufism, and he is considered a representative of the Naqshbandi order. Boborahim Mashrab's creative work is aimed at promoting Islamic values, illuminating human and divine relationships. Throughout his career, the poet wielded his pen as a ruthless enemy of hypocrisy, deceit, and slavery to the flesh. His ghazals, which reflect the spirit of rebellion against injustice, are preserved in divans, tazkiras and bayozas in various libraries around the world. His works are popular among the people under such names as "Devonai Mashrab", "Eshoni Mashrab", "Hazrati Shah Mashrab", "Eshoni Shah Mashrabi devonai Namangoniy".

The first information about the life and work of Boborahim Mashrab is found in the tazkiras of Muhammad Maleho Samarkandiy "Muzakkiri ahbob", written in 1692. In the tazkiras, the author, as a contemporary of the poet, provides brief information about where Boborahim Mashrab was born, where and from whom he studied, and in what spirit he created works.

Mashrab studies have a long history. The history of the study of the poet's works can be conditionally divided into four periods:

- 1) the period from the 17th century to the second half of the 19th century;
- 2) Work on Mashrab art during the period of the Tsarist occupation of Russia;
- 3) the period from the October Revolution to the 1980s;
- 4) Mashrab studies during the years of independence.

Mashrabning hayotiy tajribasi va ijodiy manbalari

The formation of Mashrab's work is inextricably linked with the Sufi school. He was born in Namangan, and from a young age he was interested in science and philosophy, and he talked with many sheikhs and scholars. In particular, his acquaintance with the ideas of Abdurahman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Ahmad Yassavi and Nizami enriched the poet's soul. But one of Mashrab's most important teachers is the famous Sufi, Ishq Babasi - Mulla Bazar Akhun.

Mashrab's constant travels in his life, conversations between people, and the social injustices he saw in different cities filled his worldview and poetry with a strong social content. Therefore, his poems, along with themes such as love, truth, goodness, justice, divine love, sharply criticize such evils in people's lives as injustice, hypocrisy, and ignorance.

In the poetic heritage of the poet Boborahim Mashrab, dedicated to glorifying human dignity and spiritual perfection, praising goodness and beauty, we find mature examples written in such genres as ghazal, mustazod, murabba', muhammas, musaddas, musabba, masnavi, rubai, and history. However, the poet Boborahim Mashrab, first of all, is widely known as a skilled ghazal writer and the creator of many cheerful and sonorous mustazods, playful and attractive murabba's, and muhammas expressing sympathy for the sorrows and longings of the people. Many of Boborahim Mashrab's ghazals are as simple and sonorous, passionate and touching as folk songs.

His poetry is distinguished by the following features:

The concept of divine love

Mashrab considered the most basic idea of Sufi literature - divine love - as its central theme. In his works, love for Allah, devotion to the Creator, and purification of the soul are poetically expressed. For example:

If God does not have mercy, what is the use of glorification and obedience?

If there is no faith, what is the use of charity and generosity?

Folk spirit and passionate feeling

Mashrab's language is in harmony with the language of the people: simple, fluent, sharp. The poet conveyed his thoughts not with complex philosophical expressions, but with folk verses. Therefore, in Mashrab's poetry, one can feel the melody of simple folk songs.

I saw a people who were in love,

I saw a people whose eyes were like planets at dawn,

I saw a people whose bodies were wounded by pain and suffering,

I saw a people whose hearts were pierced by oppression,

Oppression is rampant - everyone is unaware and alone

Critical spirit and courage

One of the most important aspects that distinguishes Mashrab's work from others is sharp social criticism. He condemns hypocritical Sufis, tyrannical officials, and injustice.

Although this courage cost the poet his life, it raised him to an even greater level of glory in the eyes of the people.

The idea of spiritual freedom.

Mashrab's poetry promotes the spiritual freedom of man, the purity of the soul, the inner essence of Sufism - the direct relationship between the servant and the Creator. It is known that this idea was sharply opposed by the official religious circles of that time.

Mashrab occupies a significant place in the history of Uzbek literature in several ways:

1. An expression of the people's spirit

Mashrab translated the people's pain, dreams, longing, and thirst for justice into poetic language. His poems have been mixed with folk songs for centuries in the form of oral creativity. This is one of the most important factors that kept Mashrab alive in the minds of the people.

2. A successor and innovator of mystical literature

He continued the traditions of such representatives of mysticism as Ahmad Yassavi, Suleiman Boqirghani, and Navoi, enriching them with the spirit of his time. Mashrab brought mysticism closer to people's lives from a complex philosophy.

3. A symbol of free thought and freedom

Mashrab, fearlessly expressing his opinion, became one of the founders of the free spirit in literature. His courageous words became a strong spiritual impetus for the next generation of poets.

4. Influence on modern literature

The spirit of Mashrab is felt in 20th-century Uzbek literature: such writers as Cholpon, Qodiriy, Oybek, Erkin Vohidov, Abdulla Oripov mentioned Mashrab as a symbol of freedom and truth. Even today, Mashrab's legacy serves as a source of inspiration for young writers.

In conclusion, we can say that Boborahim Mashrab is one of the great stars shining in the spiritual sky of Uzbek literature. His work is a profound expression of the people's spirit, an incomparable example of mystical literature, and a bold statement against social injustice. Mashrab's poems have not lost their relevance today: the ideas of humanity, freedom, and truthfulness in them are among the eternal values of Uzbek literature.

Literature used:

1. <http://book.uz> – Elektron adabiyotlar kutubxonasi
2. Normatova R. Mashrab she'riyati va xalq og'zaki ijodi: fil.fan. nomz...diss. Avtoreferat. – Toshkent, 2012.
3. Boborahim Mashrab. Mab dai nur / Qo'lyozma manbalardan nashrga tayyorlovchi, tadqiq qiluvchi, lug'at va izohlar tuzuvchi Ismatulloh Abdulloh / Toshkent: Fan, 1994.
4. "Mukhtarova, M. S., Namozova, S. B., & Mardonova, L. U. (2023). A Lyrical View of History. Journal of Law and Sustainable Development, 11(12), e2676.
5. www.ziyo.net